

A SIR Model to Predict the Covid-19 Outbreak in Turkey

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Abstract

In this note, we used SIR Modelling framework (susceptible, infected, removed) to predict the progress of Covid-19 epidemic in Turkey by using the empirical data between the period of March 11 2020 and April 30 2020. The system of ordinary differential equations is obtained after inserting the empirical parameters in the model. These differential equations are solved by the stiff solver in Matlab. We observed that the model fits the statistical data obtained in the considered period. We also predict the duration of the epidemic and the number of mortal cases for different ranges of parameters.

1 Introduction

An epidemic disease is an important problem for the humanity. For the purpose of showing the consequences of an epidemic, mathematical models help us to understand how infectious diseases progress. The mathematical model of infectious disease is used in order to study the mechanisms of disease. Compared with statistical methods mathematical modelling based on dynamical equations can often provide essential information of the epidemic dynamics and helps us to evaluate the controlling strategies. The earliest mathematical model of spread of disease was given by Daniel Bernoulli in 1766. This mathematical model was about the the practice of inoculating against the smallpox. The calculations from this model showed that universal inoculation against smallpox would increase the life expectancy from 26 years 7 months to 29 years 9 months [2]. William Hamer [3] and Ronald Ross [4] used the law of mass action to explain epidemic behaviour, in the early 20th century. In 1927, W. O. Kermack and A. G. McKendrick's proposed the SIR model. . The Kermack-McKendrick epidemic model was successful in predicting the behavior of outbreaks for many recorded epidemics [5].

2 The SIR Model

SIR model is one of the most commonly used models which is used to represent infectious diseases such as influenza, SARS, measles, and mumps. In this model, it is assumed that there are no death, no new born in the population, no migration into and out of the population and also that infected people are not re-infected after they have been recovered. With these assumptions there is

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a fixed population with three compartments: susceptible, $S(t)$; infected, $I(t)$; and removed, $R(t)$. The flow this model can be shown as :

Using fixed population, $N(t) = S(t) + I(t) + R(t)$, this model has following three reaction equations:

$$\begin{aligned} \frac{dS}{dt} &= -\frac{\beta}{S}I \\ \frac{dI}{dt} &= \frac{\beta}{S}I - \gamma I \\ \frac{dR}{dt} &= \gamma I \end{aligned} \tag{1}$$

$$\tag{2}$$

where $S(t)$ is the number of susceptible people, $I(t)$ represents the number of infected people and $R(t)$ denotes the number of recovered people. β is the transmission rate from susceptible condition to infectious condition and γ is the recovered rate; both are empirical constants.

3 Numerical Simulations and Prediction

In this section, We fitted the SIR model to the COVID-19 epidemic Turkey between the period of March 11 2020 and April 30 2020. As a number of susceptible, the number of tests is considered. The initial number of the infected people was taken as 1. In figure 1, the population model fits the confirmed cases within 30 days with the transmission rate $\beta = 0.00018$ and the recovered rate $\gamma = 0.01$. The prediction of the model with these rates is given in figure 2. After 30 days, rates are changing. Prediction is not compatible with the confirmed cases. For the general scenario β is taken as 0.0001667 and γ is taken as 0.03. This scenario is shown in figure 3. According to the last prediction, number of infected people reaches the maximum between 60 and 70 days.

Figure 1: Fitting of the model in 30 days

Figure 2: Prediction of the model with $\beta = 0.00018$ and $\gamma = 0.01$

Figure 3: Prediction of the population model in 300 days

4 Conclusions and Discussions

Based on available data estimation between the period March 11 2020 and April 30 2020, the SIR modelling predicts the final size of the infected people with coronavirus epidemy around 153.000.000 cases. The peak time will be on 11 May 2020. The total number of the death people will reach between 4725 and 6180 until end of the this year.

References

- [1] "Mathematical modelling of infectious disease", Wikipedia
- [2] Bernoulli, D. ; Blower, S. "An attempt at a new analysis of the mortality caused by smallpox and of the advantages of inoculation to prevent it." *Reviews in Medical Virology*, 14, 275288 (2004).

- [3] Hamer, W. *Epidemiology Old and New*. London: Kegan Paul (1928).
- [4] Ross, Ronald . *The Prevention of Malaria* (1910).
- [5] Kermack, W. O.; McKendrick, A. G. "A Contribution to the Mathematical Theory of Epidemics". *Proceedings of the Royal Society A: Mathematical, Physical and Engineering Sciences*. 115 (772): 700 (1927).